

Sample Name: PA 1-5 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: Wessling

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 83% particles are between 1-5 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- 1.4×10^{11} particles per gram
- $16125 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- S, P, Cu and Rb contaminants detected by ICP-MS
 - P, Cu and Rb $<1 \text{ }\mu\text{g/g}$
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum.
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PA spectrum with no evidence of degradation

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- $D50_v$: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- $D50_N$: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
5.27	3.33	2.28	1.77	1.42	3.98	1.4 10^{11}	16125

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using ICP-MS provided by Wessling)

Element	Concentration
S	25 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Cu	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Rb	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)